

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11178397>

TRADITIONAL CLASSIFICATION OF LESSONS. TRADITIONAL AND NON-TRADITIONAL LESSONS.

Ubaidova D.A

Senior Lecturer at BSPI

***Annotation:** The article discusses the issue of the structure of a modern lesson, the features of traditional and non-traditional lessons.*

***Key words and phrases:** classification of lessons, traditional classification, traditional and non-traditional lessons.*

A lesson is a form of organizing training with the goal of students mastering the material being studied. As we know, such a system is used in a classroom-based teaching system. We also know that Jan Komensky is the founder of pedagogical science, he is the “father of modern education.” The word lesson itself comes from ancient Russian and means “condition, completion and transaction.” What is a modern lesson? A modern lesson is, first of all, a lesson in which the teacher skillfully uses all opportunities for the development of the student’s personality, her active mental growth, deep and meaningful assimilation of knowledge.

As already noted, in the methodology of teaching the Russian language there are different classifications of lessons. The most common of them is the traditional classification, according to which, depending on the main didactic goal, lessons are divided into four main types:

- **lesson on communicating new material;**
- **lesson on consolidating knowledge, skills and abilities;**
- **a lesson in general repetition, systematization of acquired knowledge;**
- **a lesson in control.**

Each of these types of lessons has its own structural features; let’s present the diagrams of these types of lessons.

Lesson outline for communicating new material:

- organizational stage;
- stage of updating knowledge;
- stage of explaining new material;
- stage of consolidation of knowledge;

- the stage of informing students about homework and instructions on how to complete it;

- conclusions about the lesson, student assessment.

Lesson outline for consolidating knowledge, skills and abilities:

- organizational stage;

- stage of updating knowledge;

- stage of consolidation of knowledge;

- the stage of informing students about homework and instructions on how to complete it;

- conclusions about the lesson, student assessment.

Review lesson outline:

- organizational stage;

- stage of updating knowledge;

- stage of repetition, generalization of knowledge;

- the stage of informing students about homework and instructions on how to complete it;

- conclusions about the lesson, student assessment.

Control lesson outline:

- organizational stage;

- the stage of preparing students for knowledge testing;

- stage of comprehensive testing of students' knowledge;

- the stage of informing students about homework and instructions on how to complete it;

- conclusions from the lesson.

B. T. Panov in his work “Types and structure of Russian language lessons” notes that “... a specific lesson should have its own didactic objectives, which depend primarily on the purpose and type of lesson.”

According to many methodologists, the main, dominant type of Russian language lesson is a combined lesson with its diverse structural options. B. T. Panov understands by a “combined” lesson a lesson in which “the work of studying, primary consolidation and further systematization and generalization of knowledge is intelligently combined.”

In combined lessons, there is an explanation of new material, and consolidation, and repetition of what has been learned, and testing of assimilation, and homework, and checking homework.

The thematic principle in lesson organization has recently become the leading one in connection with the communicative and educational orientation

Russian language teaching. In a thematic lesson, a specific grammatical topic is learned, and the language didactic material is united by a single semantic theme.

So, combined and thematic lessons take into account the peculiarities of teaching the Russian language; they should be strived to be organically included in the system of lessons of different types.

3. In addition to traditional lessons, non-traditional (or non-standard) lessons are now widespread, which in their structure are fundamentally different from classical lessons.

Non-standard lessons include: lesson-lecture, lesson-seminar, lesson-debate, lesson-game, lesson-assessment, etc. These lessons increase interest in the educational process, add variety to it, and activate students.

K.Z. Zakiryaynov notes that non-traditional lessons “to a greater extent than traditional ones contribute to the democratization of the pedagogical process, the development of cooperation between teacher and students, as well as the development logical thinking and creative imagination of schoolchildren, instilling in them an interest in the Russian language.”

At the same time, conducting non-standard lessons is often impractical; in no case can they completely replace the main types of lessons. In addition, the genres of non-traditional lessons (seminar lesson, travel lesson, lecture lesson, etc.) should alternate.

Thus, in order to be able to properly organize the educational process when studying a topic or section of the program, it is necessary to use not just one type of lesson, but a series of lessons of different types. Each of the types of lessons we examined and their variants should find a place in the teacher’s work system.

LITERATURE

1. Methods of teaching the Russian language at school. Ed. M. T. Baranova. – M.: Publishing Center “Academy”, 2000.
2. Theory and practice of teaching the Russian language. Ed. R.B. Sabatkoeva. - M.: Publishing center "Academy", 2005.
3. Reader on the methods of the Russian language: Russian language as a subject of teaching. Comp. A. V. Tekuchev. – M., 2002
4. “Effective methods and techniques for teaching the Russian language in secondary schools” Article. Ubaidova D. A.
5. Khakimovna G. D. PHILOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF LITERARY TEXT //IMRAS. – 2024. – T. 7. – №. 2. – С. 62-65.

6. Khakimovna G. D. The Process of Pre-School Grammatical Mastering //European journal of innovation in nonformal education. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 165-169.
7. Ubaydova D. ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ВУЗОВСКОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ: Интерактивные методы обучения на уроках русского языка //Vuxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti jurnali. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
8. Убайдова Д. А. ЛИТЕРАТУРА ВТОРОЙ ПОЛОВИНЫ 19 ВЕКА: ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ //Solution of social problems in management and economy. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 51-56.
9. Nikolaevna S. E., Usmanovna R. L. The Problem of a Holistic Analysis of a Literary Text //Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 230-236.
10. Radjabova L. U. USE OF RIDDLES IN LEARNING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE //IMRAS. – 2024. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 54-57.
11. Sh B. M. Reflection of the Linguistic Picture of the World in the Phraseological Turns of the Russian Language //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 162-165.
12. Саидова М. Р., Болтаева М. Ш. Типологическое исследование односоставных предложений в русском и узбекском языках //Электронный инновационный вестник. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 24-25.
13. Алиева З. Р. ТЕОРИЯ РЕЧЕВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИКИ //SCHOLAR. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 121-126.
14. Мустафоева Л. СИНТАГМАТИЧЕСКИЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ В РУССКОЙ ЛЕКСИКЕ. ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОБОРОТЫ И ИХ ПРИЗНАКИ //Current approaches and new research in modern sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 66-